

Reflection of NAAC on Institutional Websites in Higher Educational Institutions of Affiliated Colleges of Dhulia District of Maharashtra

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Abstract:- The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is an autonomous institution that assesses and accredits higher educational institutions in India. The mandatory requirement for accreditation is that institutions must have a comprehensive website that reflects their academic and administrative activities. This study aims to analyze the reflection of NAAC on institutional websites of higher educational institutions affiliated with colleges in Dhulia district, Maharashtra. The data is collected through the structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed as per the need of NAAC, Higher Educational Institutions and researchers for institutional websites. A total of 34 institutional websites were selected for the study, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Nowadays, ICT impact on higher educational sectors. About all types of academic work is done by the ICT tools and techniques. It is mandatory by the NAAC, the academic information is uploaded on institutional website. It is available and accessible on website that is institutional website. It is benefited to all users for accessing the information at anywhere and anytime. The study suggests that institutions should prioritize their website's development and update them regularly to reflect the NAAC's accreditation requirements.

Keywords:- Higher Education, Institutional Website, NAAC

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, ICT tools and techniques are essential part in higher education for maintain the qualitative and quantitative work. The mandatory part of ICT is used in all areas of higher education for effectiveness and improve the quality work.

The global changes, particularly the impact of ICT tools and techniques on the overall functioning of higher educational institutions. This topic discusses about the reflection of NAAC on institutional website. Revised NAAC process, the important aspects of the accreditation process is the evaluation of institutional website. In recent years, the NAAC has emphasized the need for higher education institutions to maintain updated and informative websites that provide comprehensive information about the

institution, its programmes, facilities and services. The website is considered as an important communication tool for stakeholders such as students, faculties, alumni and general public. Institutional website is mandatory to all educational institutions in India for maintain the quality work and disseminate the quality information.

In order to assess the quality of institutional websites, the parameters of NAAC on various aspects such as the design of website, relevance of content, the ease of navigation, and the accessibility of information. The NAAC considers the institutional website as an important indicator of the institution's commitment to quality and transparency. Therefore, it is essential for higher education institutions to give due importance to their institutional websites and ensure that they are regularly updated with relevant and accurate information. Institutions should also strive to improve the user experience of their websites and make them accessible to all users.

National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) was established by the *University Grant Commission (UGC) in 1994*. Aim of study is to Reflect of NAAC on Institutional Websites in Higher Educational Institutions of Affiliated Colleges of Dhulia District of Maharashtra. The institutional website is to reflect and transparent the higher education system by assessment and accreditation of NAAC.

➤ Higher Education System in India

Higher Education of India is the third largest higher education system in world. The role of higher educational institution such as colleges and universities in the present time is to provide quality based education. India has a diverse higher education system that includes both public and private institutions. The system is managed by the University Grants Commission (UGC), which is the central organization responsible for coordinating, determining and maintaining standards of university education in India.

There are various types of higher education institutions in India, including universities, colleges, open universities, institutes and deemed universities. The universities can be either central, state or private universities. There are also various specialized institutions, such as India Institutes of

Technology (IITs), Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs), National Institutes of Technology (NITs) and All India Institutes of Medical Science (AIIMS)

The higher education system in India offers undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral programme in various fields, including engineering, medicine, law, management, humanities, social sciences and sciences. In India, the education system is highly competitive and students strive to get admission into the best institutions. In recent years, the government of India has undertaken various initiatives to improve the higher education system, such as the establishment of new institutions, increasing the number of seats in existing institutions and introducing reforms to enhance the quality of education. These initiatives are expected to improve the accessibility and affordability of higher education in India.

➤ *National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), Bangalore URL of NAAC- www.naac.gov.in*

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is an autonomous body established by the University Grants Commission (UGC) of India in 1994 to assess and accredit institutions of higher education in India. Its headquarters are located in Bangalore, Karnataka. Objective of NAAC is to promote quality assurance in higher education institutions in India. The council evaluates institutions based on a set of parameters and criteria such as Curriculum, teaching-learning, research, infrastructure, student support, governance, financial management and institutional values. NAAC uses a grading system ranging from A++ to D with A++ being the highest grade.

NAAC accreditation process involves a two-stage process, which includes a self-assessment report by the institution followed by an on-site peer review by a team of experts. The council has accredited over 1000 universities and colleges in India so far.

The accreditation by NAAC is highly valued in India and is a requirement for institutions to receive funding from the UGC and Rashtriya Uchhatar Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA). It also helps institutions to attract students and faculty, as well as to improve the quality of education and research

The NAAC proposes that every accredited institution should establish an *Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC)* as a quality sustenance measure. The IQAC will become a part of the institution's system and work towards realization of the goals of quality enhancement and sustenance. The work of IQAC is the first step towards internalization and institutionalization of quality enhancement initiatives. *Revised NAAC Framework has implemented since July, 2017.* Further changes in NAAC as given below

- *Establish IQAC in institution*
- *NAAC assessment and accreditation period of five years for any academic institutions*
- *Mandatory submitted online Annual Quality Assurance Report (AQAR) in every academic year before 31st December*

- *Create Institutional Login in Higher Education Institution (HEI) on the NAAC website (www.naac.gov.in)*
- *Submit Institutional Information for Quality Assurance (IIQA)*
- *Prepare Self Study Report*
- *Prepare Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics*
- *Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS)*
- *Data Validation and Verification (DVV) Process*
- *Pre-qualification stage (Pass or Fail)*
- *Preparation of Peer Team Visit*
- *38% Assessment on Qualitative Metrics by the NAAC Peer Team Visit*
- *62% Assessment on Quantitative Metrics by the NAAC*
- *Declared Final Grade*

➤ *Seven Criterion of NAAC*

- *Curricular Aspects*
- *Teaching-Learning and Evaluation*
- *Research, Innovations and Extension*
- *Infrastructure and Learning Resources*
- *Students Support and Progression*
- *Governance, Leadership and Management*
- *Institutional Values and Best Practices*

➤ *Affiliated College*

There are about 220 affiliated colleges run by the Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. The affiliated colleges divided into three districts i.e. Jalgaon, Dhule and Nandurbar. The categories of college are Arts, Commerce, Science, Social Work, Education, and Engineering and Medical colleges. Higher education provided in colleges like Under Graduate (UG), Post Graduate (PG) and Research Culture.

➤ *Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon*

Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon was established on 15 August, 1990 under the Maharashtra Act (No. XXIX) of 1989. The university is granted with University Grant Commission (UGC) recognition under section 2(f) and 12 (B) in 1993. There were three district under this university which are Jalgaon, Dhule and Nandurbar with pre-dominantly tribal area. University has 646 acres of land on a hilly terrain on the banks of the river Girna. There are **220 affiliated colleges** and 04 university recognized research centres and also vocational courses and short term skill development courses run by the university. Campus area networking through optical fiber cable and V-SAT connectivity enabled in university campus. University has well equipped knowledge resources centre.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The researcher has gone through the previous related works already done on the present topic

- *Ravikumar KI, Sasmitarani Samanta, Amiya Kumar Rath (2021)*¹ has published paper on Impact of NAAC Accreditation on Quality Improvement of Higher Education System in India: A Case Study in the State of Karnataka. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is a premier agency in India to assess and accredit the quality levels in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). It works under the ministry of education, Government of India and evaluate the quality performance of HEIs using well defined benchmarks. The importance of NAAC accreditations for HEI is to maintaining, sustaining and improving their quality.
- *Chikate, A.N. and Ghante,P.B. (2018)*² has been published the paper on Impact of NAAC's assessment and accreditation on Library Management: A Study in the field of library and information science. The research paper has uploaded on "Knowledge Librarian" An International Peer Reviewed Bilingual E-Journal (<http://www.klibjlis.com>) dated on March-April, 2018. By the researcher analyze the information about impact of assessment and accreditation by NAAC on college libraries development. NAAC is playing very important role in the development of libraries.
- *Narasanaikar,K.I. and Hangaragi, K.B. (2017)*³, have published paper on NAAC accreditation and the library improvement: Special reference to college libraries in International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development at online form (www.allsubjectjournal.com). The main purpose of this study is to examine the quality indicators framed for library in the NAAC accreditation process have provided guidelines for improving the quality of work of the entire library. In this paper quality indicators for college libraries i.e. collection, automation, services, extension activities, best practices are studied in detail with reference to set of question prepared for the library by the NAAC.
- *Objectives*
 - *To find out the impact of NAAC on overall development of higher educational institutions*
 - *To know the present status of NAAC accredited college website*
 - *To study the views of the teachers and the students through feedback towards the college website before and after NAAC's assessment*

- *To use Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Challenges (SWOC) to analyzed in entire functioning of college*
- *To fulfill the recommendations of NAAC for next reaccreditation of college*

➤ *Hypotheses*

- *There is a significant impact of NAAC on overall development of higher educational institutions*
- *There is significant impact on present status of NAAC accredited college website are in good position but there is no significant impact on without accredited college website*
- *The users regular visited to college website has been increased during and after NAAC's assessment*
- *The method of SWOC analysis is activated in college during the assessment period of NAAC*
- *The college website fulfill the recommendations of NAAC for next reaccreditation*

III. DATA COLLECTION METHODOLOGY

The research problems on reflection of NAAC on institutional website in affiliated colleges of Dhulia District to Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon will be studied by survey method and information will be collected from the stakeholders through questionnaire. The collected data and information will be analyzed by applying statistical method.

➤ *Questionnaire Design*

Questionnaire is often used for this study. Questionnaire is designed as per the research topic. Questionnaire were circulated through the post or e-mail.

➤ *Scope and Limitations*

The present study has immense scope. It is very much useful to the higher educational institutions, NAAC and Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University; Jalgaon. Thus the scope is at both national and international level.

The study is limited to 34 granted colleges of Dhulia District and affiliated to Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University; Jalgaon. Reflection of NAAC on higher educational website is measured by measuring the research outcome during assessment and accreditation of **NAAC Cycles**.

Recent Position of Institutional Website of 34 Colleges of Dhulia District Affiliated to Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon

Table 1 District: Dhule

Sr. No.	Name of College with Address	Establishment Year	URL of Institutional Website
1	Jai Hind Education Trust Sanchalit Zulal Bhilajirao Patil College, Deopur, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1982	https://zbpatil.in/
2	S.S.V.P. Sanstha's Late Karmaveer Dr.P.R.Ghogare Science College, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1967	https://prgscience.com/
3	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Bhausahab N.S.Patil Arts and Mulla Fidaalli Mulla Abdulalli Commerce College, DHULE,	1956	https://ssvpacdhuile.com
4	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Bapusaheb Shivajirao Deore College of Engineering, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1983	https://ssvpsengg.ac.in/
5	Vidya Wardhini Sabha's Vidyawardhini Arts Commerce and Science College, DHULE , Dist.Dhule. Pin 424 001.	1966	http://vwscollegedhuile.ac.in/
6	Dhule Education Society's M.D.Palesha Commerce College, DHULE. Pin 424 001.	1984	--
7	West Khandesh Dalit Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar Memorial College of Law, Deopur, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1975	https://dbamlaw.in/
8	Dhule Education Society's College of Education, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1961	https://www.descoed.org/
9	Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra's Mahila Arts College, DHULE. Pin 424 002.	1992	https://www.aykk.org/mahila-institute.php
10	Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra Sanchalit College of Education, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	1986	https://www.aykk.org/
11	Social & Cultural Association's Smt. Narmadabai Nago Chaudhari Arts, Commerce & Science College, KUSUMBA , Dist:Dhule.	1986	https://smtnnckkusumba.org/
12	Jawahar Shikshan Prasarak Sanstheche College of Education Gartad, Dist- Dhule	1986	--
13	Gram Vikas Mandal Navalnagar Sanchalit Krantivir Navalbhau Arts College, NAVALNAGAR, Dist: Dhule.	1993	--
14	Gangamai Education Trust's Arts, Commerce & Science College, NAGAON, Dist:Dhule.	1993	https://gangamaisenior.org.in/
15	Samta Shikshan Prasarak Santha Pune, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar College of Social Work, MORANE, Dist.- Dhule.	1995	https://drbacsw.edu.in/
16	Bahujan Samaj Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Arts, Commerce & Science College, SONGIR, Dist:Dhule.	1996	https://bsspmasc.com/
17	Vidya Vikas Mandal's Sitaram Govind Patil Arts, Science & Commerce College, SAKRI , Dist.Dhule.	1971	https://www.sgpcsakri.com/
18	Pimpalner Education Society's Karm. A.M.Patil Arts, Commerce Kai. Annasaheb N.K.Patil Science College, PIMPALNER, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	1983	--
19	Nijampur Jaitane Shikshan Prasarak.Mandal's Aadarsh Arts College, NIJAMPUR-JAITANE, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	1995	www.njspmaca.in
20	Navodaya Shaikshanik Sanstha's Uttamrao Patil Arts & Science College, DAHIWEL, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	1995	http://upcdahivel.ac.in/
21	Adishakti Dhandai Mata Shikshan Prasarak Sanstha's Arts & Science College, MHASDI, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	1998	https://admsps.org/
22	Trimurti Education Society's Smt.Vimalbai Uttamrao Patil Arts & Late Dr.Bhaskar Sadashiv Desale Science College, SAKRI, Dist.Dhule.	1998	https://vupabsdscsakri.co.in/
23	Kisan Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's S.P.D.M. Arts, Commerce & Science College , SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	1962	http://spdm.ac.in/
24	Shirpur Education Society's Smt.H.R.Patel Arts Mahila	1990	https://hrpamcollege.org/

	College, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.		
25	The Shirpur Education Society's R.C.Patel College of Education, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	1990	https://www.rcpcoedn.org/
26	R.C.Patel Educational Trust's R.C.Patel Arts, Commerce & Science College, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	1991	https://rcpasc.ac.in/
27	R.C.Patel Educational Trust's Institute of Management Research and Development, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	1995	--
28	Annapurna Devi Vidya Prasarak Sanstha Sanchalit Arts College, THALNER, Tq.Shirpur, Dist.Dhule.	2000	https://avpsthalner.org/
29	Shirpur Education Society's R.C. Patel Institute of Technology, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	1995	https://www.rcpit.ac.in/
30	AVPSS Arts College, Thalner, Shirpur, Dhule	2000	https://avpsthalner.org/
31	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Late S.D.Patil Alias Baburao Dada Arts, Commerce & Late M.D.Sisode Science College, SHINDKHEDA, Dist:Dhule.	1970	https://ssvpsacs.ac.in/
32	Swoddharak Vidyarthi Sanstha's Arts & Science College, DONDAICHA, Tq. Shindkheda, Dist.Dhule.	1984	http://www.dadasahebrawalcollege.ac.in/
33	Gramin Vikas Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Late M.D.Sisode alias Bhausaheb Arts and Commerce College, NARDANA, Tq.Shindkheda, Dist:Dhule.	1990	--
34	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Smt. P.B.Bagal Arts & Commerce College, DONDAICHA, Tq. Shindkheda, Dist:Dhule.	1970	--

➤ *Faculty wise 34 NAAC Accredited Colleges of Dhule District.*

There are 27 colleges have active higher educational website out of 34 colleges. Remaining 07 colleges found no website.

- *Single Faculty:*
- *Arts: 04*
- *Science: 01*
- *Commerce: 01*
- *Double Faculty: 10*
- *Multiple Faculty: 12 Colleges*
- *Law Faculty: 01*
- *Education: 01*
- *Social Work: 01*
- *Engineering: 02*
- *Management: 01*

Table 2 Type of the College

Type of HEIs	Affiliated	Autonomous	Government	Private
34	34	0	0	0

Table 3 Website Domain of Colleges

No. of Colleges	ac.in	.in	.edu	.org	.com	Without Website
34	08	06	00	09	04	07

➤ *Impact of NAAC on Colleges at Dhule District*

During and after NAAC accreditation, it is found that the colleges have lot of changes through the assessment and accreditation of NAAC. Frequently revised of NAAC manual by the NAAC for improving, enhancing, maintaining and sustaining the quality work in colleges and universities Recently, more than 20 college websites are updated.

Table 4 Impact of NAAC on Colleges at Dhule District

Sr. No.	Area of Development in HEI Website	Before NAAC	During and After NAAC	No. of College have website	No. of College have no website	Percentage
1	HEI Website	No	Yes	27	7	79
2	NAAC in Main Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
3	IQAC in Main Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
	AQAR in Sub Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79

	IQAC Minutes in Sub Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
4	Library in Main Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
5	Facilities in Main Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
6	Academic in Main Menu	No	Yes	27	7	79
7	NIRF	No	Yes	7	7	21
8	Feedback	No	Yes	27	7	79
9	Events	No	Yes	27	7	79
10	Extension Activities	No	Yes	27	7	79
11	Research	No	Yes	27	7	79
12	Best Practices	No	Yes	27	7	79

Table 5 Current Position of Accreditation Status of Colleges at Dhule District

No. of Colleges	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
34	34 Accredited	23 Accredited	10 Accredited	3 Accreditation

Table 6 Recent Updates of NAAC Grade of Colleges at Dhule District

Sr. No.	Name of College with Address	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
1	Jai Hind Education Trust Sanchalit Zulal Bhilajirao Patil College, Deopur, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	July 2003 Grade B+	Jan.2011 Grade B	2018 Grade B++	Accreditation Valid Up to 2023
2	S.S.V.P. Sanstha's Late Karmaveer Dr.P.R.Ghogare Science College, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	Sept.2003 Grade B++	March 2011 Grade A	2019 Grade A+	--
3	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Bhusaheb N.S.Patil Arts and Mulla Fidaalli Mulla Abdulalli Commerce College, DHULE,	May 2004 Grade B++	Feb.2014 Grade B	Feb.2021 Grade C	--
4	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Bapusaheb Shivajirao Deore College of Engineering, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	2018 Grade B+	Accreditation Valid Up to 2023	--	--
5	Vidya Wardhini Sabha's Vidyawardhini Arts Commerce and Science College, DHULE , Dist.Dhule. Pin 424 001.	May 2004 Grade B+	Sept.2014 Grade B	SSR Submitted	--
6	Dhule Education Society's M.D.Palesha Commerce College, DHULE. Pin 424 001.	May 2004 Grade B+	Jan.2013 Grade B	--	--
7	West Khandesh Dalit Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar Memorial College of Law, Deopur, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	April 2011 Grade B	SSR Submitted	--	--
8	Dhule Education Society's College of Education, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	Nov.2004 Grade B+	Jan.2013 Grade B	--	--
9	Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra's Mahila Arts College, DHULE. Pin 424 002.	May 2004 Grade C++	2016 Grade C	Accreditation Valid Up to 2021	--
10	Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra Sanchalit College of Education, DHULE, Dist.Dhule.	Grade B+	--	--	--
11	Social & Cultural Association's Smt. Narmadabai Nago Chaudhari Arts, Commerce & Science College, KUSUMBA , Dist:Dhule.	Sept.2016 Grade B	Nov. 2021 Grade B+	--	--
12	Jawahar Shikshan Prasarak Sanstheche College of Education Gartad, Dist- Dhule	Grade B++	--	--	--
13	Gram Vikas Mandal Navalnagar Sanchalit Krantivir Navalbhau Arts College, NAVALNAGAR, Dist: Dhule.	Feb.2005 Grade C	--	--	--
14	Gangamai Education Trust's Arts, Commerce & Science College, NAGAON, Dist:Dhule.	Sept.2004 Grade C+	SSR Submitted	--	--
15	Samta Shikshan Prasarak Santha Pune, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar College of Social Work, MORANE, Dist.- Dhule.	2015 Grade B	2020 Grade B++	--	--
16	Bahujan Samaj Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Arts, Commerce & Science College, SONGIR, Dist:Dhule.	Jan.2013 Grade B	SSR Submitted	--	--
17	Vidya Vikas Mandal's Sitaram Govind Patil Arts, Science & Commerce College, SAKRI , Dist.Dhule.	Oct.2003 Grade C++	Oct.2013 Grade C	Sept. 2022 Grade A	--
18	Pimpalner Education Society's Karm. A.M.Patil Arts, Commerce Kai. Annasaheb N.K.Patil Science	Feb.2005 Grade B	Sept.2015 Grade B	Accreditation Valid Up to 2020	--

	College, PIMPALNER, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.				
19	Nijampur Jaitane Shikshan Prasarak.Mandal's Aadarsh Arts College, NIJAMPUR-JAITANE, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	Jan.2009 Grade C	Sept.2016 Grade C	Jan.2023 Grade A	--
20	Navodaya Shaikshanik Sanstha's Uttamrao Patil Arts & Science College, DAHIWEL, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	Sept.2003 Grade B	--	--	--
21	Adishakti Dhandai Mata Shikshan Prasarak Sanstha's Arts & Science College, MHASDI, Tq.Sakri, Dist.Dhule.	Jan.2016 Grade B	Accreditation Valid Up to 2021	--	--
22	Trimurti Education Society's Smt.Vimalbai Uttamrao Patil Arts & Late Dr.Bhaskar Sadashiv Desale Science College, SAKRI, Dist.Dhule.	March 2012 Grade C	SSR Submitted	--	--
23	Kisan Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's S.P.D.M. Arts, Commerce & Science College, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	May 2004 Grade C++	2016 Grade B	Accreditation Valid Up to 2021	--
24	Shirpur Education Society's Smt.H.R.Patel Arts Mahila College, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	Sept.2004 Grade B	March 2015 A	Accreditation Valid Up to 2020	--
25	The Shirpur Education Society's R.C.Patel College of Education, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	2004 Grade B++	2016 Grade A	Accreditation Valid Up to 2021	--
26	R.C.Patel Educational Trust's R.C.Patel Arts, Commerce & Science College, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	May 2004 Grade B	Feb 2014 Grade B	2018 Grade B++	Accreditation Valid Up to 2023
27	R.C.Patel Educational Trust's Institute of Management Research and Development, SHIRPUR, Dist.Dhule.	2019 Grade B+	Accreditation Valid Up to 2024	--	--
28	Annapurna Devi Vidya Prasarak Sanstha Sanchalit Arts College, THALNER, Tq.Shirpur, Dist.Dhule.	2017 Grade C	Accreditation Valid Up to 2022	--	--
29	Shirpur Education Society's R.C. Patel Institute of Technology, SHIRPUR, Dist:Dhule.	2017 Grade A	Accreditation Valid Up to 2022	--	--
30	AVPSS Arts College,Thalner,Shirpur,Dhule	Not Yet NAAC Assessment and Accreditation			
31	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Late S.D.Patil Alias Baburao Dada Arts, Commerce & Late M.D.Sisode Science College, SHINDKHEDA, Dist:Dhule.	Sept.2003 Grade B	March 2011 Grade B	2018 Grade B	Accreditation Valid Up to 2023
32	Swoddharak Vidyarthi Sanstha's Arts & Science College, DONDAICHA, Tq. Shindkheda, Dist.Dhule.	Feb.2005 Grade B	2015 Grade A	--	--
33	Gramin Vikas Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Late M.D.Sisode alias Bhausahab Arts and Commerce College, NARDANA, Tq.Shindkheda, Dist:Dhule.	Feb.2005 Grade C++	--	--	--
34	Shri. Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Sanstha's Smt. P.B.Bagal Arts & Commerce College, DONDAICHA, Tq. Shindkheda, Dist:Dhule.	Preparing IIQA Report			

Table 7 Feedback of Teachers and Students on Reflection of NAAC on Institutional Website and Improve Quality Culture

Sr. No.	Respondent	Reflection of NAAC on Institutional Website and Improve Quality Culture		
		Yes	No	Maybe
1	Teacher	31	2	1
2	Student	29	2	3

Table 8 Fulfil the NAAC Recommendation by the College

Sr. No.	Respondent	Impact of NAAC on College Website and Improve Quality Culture		
		Yes	No	Maybe
1	Principal	31	3	0
2	Teacher	24	6	4
3	Student	22	9	3
4	Alumni	21	8	5
5	Parent	18	11	5

IV. CONCLUSION

Institutions can demonstrate their commitment to quality and transparency as well as enhance and maintain the work culture during and after the NAAC accreditation. NAAC assessment and accreditation of Higher Educational Institution is mandatory to improve the quality in educational system. It is concluded that the reflection of NAAC is to improve the quality of higher education in India continuously. It does this by conducting accreditation and assessment process, which provide authoritative and reliable feedback on the quality of an institution. The reflection of NAAC on institutional websites are to be essential for visibility and transparency of work culture, facilities and services of college. It should be accessible to users from anywhere and anytime. The study has found about 27 colleges have own website and remained 07 does not have website out of 34 colleges at Dhule district. It is considered that the Impact of NAAC is ongoing and continuous process for quality assessment of colleges.

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